

MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING
ON
FORMATION OF THE NORWEGIAN CONSORTIUM
FOR
PARTICIPATION IN THE EUROPEAN DISTRIBUTED SYSTEM OF SCIENTIFIC
COLLECTIONS (DiSSCo)

Natural History Museum, University of Oslo, duly represented by Tone Lindheim.

NTNU University Museum, duly represented by Reidar Andersen.

University Museum of Bergen, University of Bergen, duly represented by Henrik von Achen.

Tromsø University Museum, University of Tromsø -The Arctic University of Norway, duly represented by Marit Anne Hauan.

Hereinafter the ‘Signatories’, considering

- The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), has been set up to promote the scientific integration of Europe and to strengthen its international outreach. The ESFRI roadmap is identifying and prioritising the European Research Infrastructures (RIs) on a competitive basis. Inclusion of the European Natural History Collections in the ESFRI roadmap will support the collections in further achieving their strategic goals relevant to the increase of their contribution to and influence on scientific research in the context of the European Research Area.
- Natural history collections are an integral part of the European natural and cultural capital. For maximising the value and impact of European natural history collections it is critical that collection facilities join forces at both national and European level as a European Distributed Research Infrastructure. It is important that they work together to provide seamless access to the information, expertise and knowledge linked to the collections held across Europe. By doing so, European collections will transform into a pillar that underpins scientific excellence and industrial innovation in response to societal challenges.
- The forthcoming ESFRI roadmap update (2018) deadline for submission of full applications is expected within 2017. To successfully apply, natural history collection facilities will need to closely collaborate, forming national consortia that will strive to secure political support and/or financial commitment from national governments, and facilitate and support the development of the application package.

agree as follows:

Article 1
PURPOSE AND NATURE OF AGREEMENT

- (1) The purpose of this Memorandum of Understanding, hereinafter referred to as ‘MoU’, is to state the intent of the Signatories to take common steps towards:
 - a. The construction of an homogeneous group of national facilities constituting a National Task Force, that will act jointly to participate in the development and submission of the proposal for the inclusion of Natural History Collections in the ESFRI roadmap update (2018) as a Distributed System of Scientific Collections

- (DiSSCo),
- b. the construction and operation of Distributed System of Scientific Collections as a European Research Infrastructure under the provisions of the ESFRI and the DiSSCo consortium members.
- (2) Nothing in this MoU is deemed to constitute an agency or any kind of formal grouping or entity between the Signatories.
 - (3) Nothing in this MoU is deemed to constitute binding obligation among the signatories and/or towards any third party under the national or international public law.
 - (4) The Signatories agree not to withhold information that is relevant to the implementation of this MoU.

Article 2 PARTICIPATION

- (1) Each Signatory participates on an equal basis to the group of Signatories, hereinafter referred as the 'Consortium'. The Consortium will act as the national agent for the construction and operation of the Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DiSSCo) European research infrastructure.
- (2) Each Signatory recognises the coordinating role of the DiSSCo Proposal Coordination Team in developing and submitting the DiSSCo proposal to the ESFRI roadmap update procedure for 2018.
- (3) Each Signatory declares to evaluate the possibility of
 - a. contributing resources, in-kind and/or in-cash for the development of the DiSSCo proposal,
 - b. providing institutional incentives to members of staff to contribute to the preparation of the proposal material.
- (4) Each Signatory will make efforts to accurately and timely provide information on collections held, including, but not limited to, data on the size, accessibility and usage of collections, and the associated available information (such as images, genomic information and others), where this data is readily available and disclosure of such information does not oppose any established institutional policies, or any national or international law.
- (5) Each Signatory will facilitate Consortium actions aiming at securing political support or financial commitment for the DiSSCo project. These actions can aim towards Ministries and/or Departments of national Governments, national Research Councils and Funders or other stakeholders at national and international level.

Article 3 ACCESSION

- (1) The Signatories will pursue an inclusive approach to this MoU, aiming at the enlargement of the Consortium with new stakeholders.
- (2) For each new party to join the Consortium a formal agreement is required.

Article 4 REPRESENTATION

- (1) The Signatories agree for Natural History Museum, University of Oslo to act as the

Representative of the Consortium, hereinafter referred as the 'Consortium Representative'.

- (2) The Consortium Representative is responsible for consulting and securing consent from the Signatories in all cases where acting by the authority of the Consortium.
- (3) The Consortium Representative is responsible for organising the National Task Force, a group of individuals to act as contact points and provide support for DiSSCo, in alignment with the paragraphs of Articles 1 and 2.
- (4) The National Task Force can represent the Consortium in internal and public meetings relevant to DiSSCo.
- (5) The Consortium Representative can be:
 - a. Permanently replaced, following written consent of all Signatories,
 - b. Temporarily replaced, following informal consensus between all Signatories.
- (6) The Consortium Representative can sign formal and informal agreements, representing the Consortium, for the purposes of the DiSSCo proposal preparation, submission and implementation, and works closely with the DiSSCo Proposal Coordination Team as per the requirements of the application, including the preparation, submission and evaluation process.
- (7) The Consortium Representative jointly with the National Task Force take responsibility for duly and timely informing the Consortium on developments relevant to the DiSSCo proposal preparation, submission and outcome.

Article 5 ENTRY INTO FORCE AND TERMINATION

- (1) This MoU comes into effect between the Signatories as of the date of the second signature. It comes into effect for each additional Signatory after the said date as of the date of signature by the said additional Signatory.
- (2) The effect of this MoU will automatically be terminated on
 - a. Failure to successfully submit an application to the ESFRI 2018 roadmap update
 - b. Unsuccessful (failure to be included in the ESFRI 2018 roadmap) outcome of the DiSSCo application for the ESFRI 2018 roadmap update,
- (3) Other than termination provided in Article 8 below, Signatories may decide to terminate this MoU earlier than that declared in the two optional criteria specified in (2) above. In such a case, the Signatories deciding on the termination shall inform the other Signatories in writing, subject to a three-month prior notification. The remaining Signatories may decide that the MoU shall remain effective between them (provided that at least two (2) Signatories remain).
- (4) Each Signatory will favourably evaluate the possibility of an amendment to this MoU when DiSSCo officially enters the ESFRI roadmap. The amendment will further clarify the rights and responsibilities of all Consortium members under the new framework derived from DiSSCo entering the ESFRI update 2018.

Article 6 AMENDMENT AND ASSIGNMENT

- (1) Any modification of this MoU requires the written and signed consent of all the Signatories hereto to become effective.

- (2) No rights or obligations of any of the Signatories arising from this MoU may be assigned or transferred in whole or in part to any third party without the explicit and written consent of the other Signatories.
- (3) Annexes of this MoU form an integral part thereof.

Article 7
LANGUAGE

- (1) This MoU is drawn up in English, the language which governs all documents, notices, meetings and processes relative hereto.

Article 8
RESOLUTION OF DISPUTES

- (1) Any dispute that might arise concerning this MoU shall be settled amicably. If no amicable solution is deemed possible, the Signatories shall agree to the termination of this MoU.

SIGNATURES

This Memorandum of Understanding includes eight (8) Articles and two (2) Annexes, is signed, by the duly authorised undersigned representatives in five identical original copies. One copy is retained by each of the Signatories and one copy will be forwarded to the DiSSCo Proposal Coordination Team for its acknowledgement and further relations at the following address, that will retain it:

DiSSCo Proposal Coordination Team
c/o Dimitrios Koureas
Natural History Museum London
Cromwell road
SW7 5BD London
UNITED KINGDOM

Name of the Signatory: Natural History Museum, University of Oslo

Name of the legal representative: Tone Lindheim

Signature of the legal representative:

Date: 22.3.2017

Name of the Signatory: NTNU University Museum

Name of the legal representative: Reidar Andersen

Signature of the legal representative: _____

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c/o Dimitrios Koureas
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Cromwell road
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Name of the Signatory: Natural History Museum, University of Oslo

Name of the legal representative: Tone Lindheim

Signature of the legal representative: Tone Lindheim

Date: 22.03.2017.

Name of the Signatory: NTNU University Museum

Name of the legal representative: Reidar Andersen

Signature of the legal representative: Reidar Andersen

Date: _____

Name of the Signatory: University Museum of Bergen, University of Bergen

Name of the legal representative: Henrik von Achen

Signature of the legal representative: _____

Date: _____

Name of the Signatory: Tromsø University Museum, University of Tromsø -The Arctic University of Norway

Name of the legal representative: Marit Anne Hauan

Signature of the legal representative: _____

Date: 6.3.2017

Date: _____

Name of the Signatory: University Museum of Bergen, University of Bergen

Name of the legal representative: Henrik von Achen

Signature of the legal representative: _____

Date: 7/3 2017

Name of the Signatory: Tromsø University Museum, University of Tromsø -The Arctic University of Norway

Name of the legal representative: Marit Anne Hauan

Signature of the legal representative: _____

Date: _____

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ANNEX A
DiSSCo high-level summary of concept and approach

In the Distributed System of Scientific Collections - DiSSCo - partners from 18 European countries join forces to realize one ambitious shared goal: the transformation of Europe's Natural History Collections into a pan-European Research Infrastructure; a sustainable pillar of scientific excellence and industrial innovation in response to current and anticipated societal challenges. DiSSCo sets out a clear roadmap and a comprehensive action plan, which will bring European Natural History Collections at the forefront of science and innovation.

Why a Research Infrastructure?

Natural History Collections are an integral part of the global natural and cultural capital. In Europe alone, there are more than *1.5 billion* biological and geological specimens, preserved by numerous institutions. The information extracted from these collections is essential to scientific research and innovation. From Human health and wellbeing, food security, sustainable agriculture and the bio-based economy to climate change monitoring.

For Europe's Natural History Collections to reach their full potential relevant information from specimens must be extracted, connected, aggregated and made freely accessible, at a scale analogous to the challenges addressed. In the past two decades European institutions, holding Natural History Collections, have invested in jointly addressing technical and socio-cultural barriers to integrated collection access, including digitisation, and data mobilisation.

However, the fast pace of technological development and the holistic understanding of life on earth impose a quicker and multidisciplinary response. To effectively and timely meet the needs of researchers, policy makers and industrial actors for large scale and open bio and geo-diversity data, Natural History Collections will need to embark on an unprecedented digitisation and data mobilisation effort. The sheer magnitude of this effort requires pan-European collaboration and harmonisation of activities across borders.

It is only by achieving the needed economies of scope and scale that European Natural History Collections will maximise their impact, operate in a coherent and synergetic mode and serve a new key role within science and society.

Europe: Leading the world's Natural History Collections but lagging in collections' impact

Europe is today a world leader in maintaining Natural History Collections. European institutions hold more than 50% of the global Natural History specimens and represent 80% of the described diversity worldwide. However, Europe remains at the tail of regions where coordinated digitisation and data provision infrastructures have been established.

With countries, like the USA, China and Australia already ahead, European Member States need to join forces and **develop a pan-European Research Infrastructure, tooling-up its researchers with the much needed data, services and training.**

A Research Infrastructure will clear goals

Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Fully digitise 150 million specimens through a distributed and high-throughput digitisation programme across European NHCs• Produce harmonised & interoperable data across participating facilities
Policies and Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Jointly develop new and harmonise existing institutional (data and access) policies• Provide training programme to improve digital skills and competencies across NHC professionals• Create a registry of scientific experts across Europe and facilitate cross-border mobility
Data Architecture & Applications	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Create a panEuropean registry of specimens across participating facilities• Maximise digitisation throughput rates (automation/robotics) and lower costs• Simple to use and user-oriented Web services to gain better understanding of NHC data
Physical & Digital Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Create interoperable national nodes (data portals) that provide access to each country's diversity of biological and geological resources• Develop a central (innovation) hub enabling access to European digitised collections• Develop and operate a distributed system of industrial-scale digitisation facilities
Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Develop a Central Coordination Office to orchestrate and harmonise activities and seek efficiencies across the NHC facilities• Coordinate and support a European programme for physical access to collections

The pillars of DiSSCo

The development of DiSSCo will rely on three pillars:

1. **Digitising and mobilising content and providing access, tools and services**
2. **Harmonising data policies, processes and workflows**
3. **Enhancing skills and engaging communities**

Natural History Collections will go beyond their capacity to operate as part of a network, and interoperate, leveraging current resources and achieving efficiencies by using common facilities and agreeing upon policies.

DiSSCo partners will function as a system of distributed facilities, forming a pan-European Research Infrastructure that adds value to science, industry, and society at large.

The five steps to success

Successful inclusion to the European roadmap for Research Infrastructures (ESFRI roadmap) will enable the consortium of Natural History Collections to implement a series of centrally coordinated and interdependent programmes in order to meet its objectives. This Preparatory Phase (PP) consists of three key programmes (Innovation, Consolidation and Construction).

DiSSCo in the European RI landscape

In the current landscape of RIs, DiSSCo occupies a well-defined space, clearly linked to adjacent (related) initiatives. It will serve as a primary data and expertise provider, directly linked to initiatives like LifeWatch. While other initiatives may provide observational (as GBIF) or experimental data (such as EPOS), or contribute to a better modelling (like LifeWatch), the new RI DiSSCo will support and complement those by providing the backbone that enables the historical track and facilitates the shaping of the future. The sequence of data analysis will then be cycled completed, by covering the stable identification systems with those that integrate observation and refinement schemes to effectively respond and further anticipate how to ensure the sustainability of our natural diversity globally.

DiSSCo expanding network

The current (as of July 2016) network of participating countries is comprised of 18 European member states and Associated Countries.

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ANNEX B

Responsibilities and membership of the DiSSCo Proposal Coordination Team

Role and Responsibilities

The Coordination Team is responsible for the successful implementation of the agreed upon action plan.

In particular, the Coordination Team:

- Implements the agreed action plan to the agreed standards and deadlines;
- Ensures the effective preparation and delivery of all the proposal's elements;
- Is responsible for the submission and post-submission actions of the proposal;
- Invites experts to form Working Groups and monitors their activity and outcomes;
- Drafts the agendas for the Steering Committee meetings;
- Assesses the overall implementation progress;
- Coordinates the work of the National Task Forces and provides guidance on an ad-hoc basis;
- Interacts with ESFRI officials and delegates to advocate the initiative and collate pre-submission feedback;
- Reviews the overall progress of efforts at national level;
- Liaises with all internal and external stakeholders as required;
- Represents the consortium to external forums and stakeholders as required.

Membership

The Coordination Team consists of the Project Manager (PM) and two **three** deputy Project Managers (DPM). The Coordination Team can appoint people to work on supporting tasks for the Coordination Team in administration and coordination.

The PM is overall responsible for the implementation of the project tasks. It reports directly to the Steering Committee and manages all human resources related to the implementation of the project. The PM and DPM review the deliverables, ensuring their quality and suitability to the overall ESFRI requirements. When required the PM or any of the DPMs may represent the Coordination Team or the Consortium and acts as an ambassador of the project to identified stakeholders.

The PM is responsible for the process management. In consultation with the DPMs the PM sets a detailed planning for the remaining project runtime and ensures understanding of, and agreement on this planning among all partners and key stakeholders. The PM ensures timely delivery of each deliverable from the Working Groups, and National Task Forces (national nodes). The PM timely informs all of them about potential risks and bottlenecks regarding the working schedule and the means available to uphold it.

The coordination team is responsible for a proper and transparent project administration. The coordination team maintains the digital project environment used in DiSSCo. The coordination team secures all input generated throughout the project in a way that is transparent and logical to project partners and stakeholders.